

RAPID-DM: A DigitalMicrograph[®] script for on-site indexing of zone axis aligned electron diffraction patterns of cubic lattices

Vasilis A. Maroufidis (ORCID 0009-0003-0915-9894) and Thomas E. Weirich (ORCID 0000-0001-5539-0534) *

RWTH Aachen University, Central Facility for Electron Microscopy (GFE), Ahornstr. 55, D-52074 Aachen, Germany.

* Correspondence e-mail: weirich@gfe.rwth-aachen.de
phone: +49 241 80-24349
fax: +49 241 80-22313

Key words

Electron diffraction, zone axis spot pattern, orientation determination, cubic symmetry, ratio method, DigitalMicrograph Script, automated indexing

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interests or personal relationships that influence the work reported in this contribution.

Abstract

A DigitalMicrograph[®] script RAPID-DM (RAtio method Pattern InDexing) has been developed, which allows instant on-site indexing of zone-axis electron diffraction patterns of cubic lattices using the R_n ratio principle. In addition to indexing spot electron diffraction patterns, the program is also capable of indexing Kikuchi patterns taken from or near a zone axis. Both cases are demonstrated by examples for silicon. The program has a guided workflow and requires only three user-defined lines or Kikuchi bands for indexing. RAPID-DM has been extensively tested and verified to work reliably with both calibrated and non-calibrated zone-axis patterns and allows the user to easily evaluate whether the material under examination is cubic, pseudo-cubic or neither. For calibrated patterns, the program provides an average value of the cubic lattice parameter, which can serve for phase identification in connection with a structural database, or it can simply be used to verify the material under investigation. In its current state, the developed script has proved to be a valuable add-on to the DigitalMicrograph[®] platform in the authors' service laboratory, as it greatly simplifies on-site crystallographic analysis of electron diffraction patterns of steels, alloys and ceramics, which frequently form cubic or pseudo-cubic structures.

1. Introduction

Relatively small unit cell phases with cubic or pseudo-cubic symmetry still dominate most transmission electron microscopy (TEM) studies of metallic alloy systems, ceramics and semiconductors (West, 2024), and many more technologically relevant materials with cubic symmetry are likely to be discovered in the future (Zhao et al., 2021). Therefore, reliable information on the crystallographic orientation of the sample under investigation is often needed on site for the correct set-up of a specific experiment. A standard method for aligning a zone axis of a crystal parallel to the incident electron beam is selected area electron diffraction (SAED), which involves tilting the sample in the TEM along the two goniometer axes until a symmetrical electron diffraction spot pattern is obtained. In addition, Kikuchi diffraction taken under non-exact parallel beam conditions and/or from thicker regions can be applied for the final exact orientation of the sample (Heimendahl, 1980; Champness, 2001; Fultz & Howe, 2002). For crystals which belong to the cubic crystal system there are basically two simple approaches that use the special geometrical relations of the cubic (reciprocal) lattice for indexing. This can be done either by visual inspection and comparison of the geometry of the experimental zonal axis electron diffraction patterns with standard spot patterns (Eichen et al.; Andrews et al., 1968; Edington, 1975; Champness, 2001; Spence & Zuo, 1992; Fultz & Howe, 2002; Williams & Carter, 2009; Weirich, 2024a), or by using measured distances (or interplanar d -values) and angles with the R_n ratio method, e.g. (Heimendahl, 1980; Fultz & Howe, 2002). The latter method was developed and first applied by the pioneer of X-ray diffraction, William Lawrence Bragg, in 1913 (Bragg, 1913) and has recently been revisited and systematized for application on SAED patterns (Weirich, 2024b).

While all these methods have proven to work well for the post-evaluation of SAED patterns of cubic materials, they are less suitable for instant on-site crystallographic analysis in the TEM laboratory. To fill this gap, an open-source ImageJ script has recently been developed (Weirich, 2024c) that allows rapid indexing of known and unknown zonal axis patterns of cubic lattices by exploiting the R_n ratio principle. However, due to the restrictions imposed by most microscope manufacturers who do not allow modification or installation of additional software packages such as the ImageJ environment on the TEM computer, it was requested that the code be translated into the DigitalMicrograph® scripting language (www.gatan.com) in order to be able to use R_n ratio approach on the same PC as used for image acquisition with the GATAN camera.

2. The R_n ratio method for indexing cubic zone axis patterns

The R_n ratio method uses the relationship in Eq. (1), where r_A and r_B represent the distances of the diffraction spots A and B from the pattern center. The corresponding interplanar distances are denoted by d , and the triplets hkl are the Laue indices of these reflections. The sum of the squared indices is often replaced by N to further simplify the relationship.

$$\frac{r_B^2}{r_A^2} = \frac{d_A^2}{d_B^2} = \frac{(h_B^2 + k_B^2 + l_B^2)}{(h_A^2 + k_A^2 + l_A^2)} = \frac{N_B}{N_A} \quad \text{eq(1)}$$

The goal of ratio indexing is to find a match between the experimentally determined ratio r_B / r_A and the calculated ratio $\sqrt{N_B} / \sqrt{N_A}$. The therefrom obtained trial set of Laue indices can be used to calculate the zone axis orientation $[uvw]$ along the incident beam direction from the cross product in eq. (2).

$$\begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{bmatrix} = A \times B = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & h_A & h_B \\ 1 & k_A & k_B \\ 1 & l_A & l_B \end{vmatrix} \quad \text{eq(2)}$$

In the following step each zone axis is checked with eq(3) for agreement with the experimentally determined interplanar angle $\phi_{(A-B)}$ between the two reflection spots A and B.

$$\phi_{A-B} = \arccos \left[\frac{A \cdot B}{|A| \cdot |B|} \right] \quad \text{eq(3)}$$

To confirm that the found match is real and not accidental, the ratio and angle check is repeated for another diffraction spot C. Thus, the minimum information required from the experimental data for reliable indexing a zone axis pattern of a material with cubic lattice are the measured distances r_A, r_B, r_C and the angles $\phi_{(A-B)}$ and $\phi_{(A-C)}$ between them. Once the reflections A and B have been defined, the Laue indices of reflection C can be calculated from the hkl indices of spots A and B using eq(4) (see also Weirich, 2024b; 2024c). It is important to note that this only leads to a reliable result if the reflections that are used represent the three shortest reciprocal space vectors in the diffraction pattern. This matter is outlined in more detail in section 3, which describes the rules for correctly addressing the reflections in a SAED pattern.

$$\begin{bmatrix} h_C \\ k_C \\ l_C \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} h_A \\ k_A \\ l_A \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} h_B \\ k_B \\ l_B \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{eq(4)}$$

In cases, when the camera constant CC is provided by the user, the experimental distances r (in pixel units) can be used to calculate the length of the reciprocal vector g_{hkl} and the interplanar d_{hkl} spacing using eq(5). The corresponding lattice parameter a is then obtained from eq(6) if the hkl indices for a diffraction spot is known.

$$g_{hkl} = r_{hkl}/CC = 1/d_{hkl} \quad \text{eq(5)}$$

$$a = d_{hkl} \cdot \sqrt{N_{hkl}} \quad \text{eq(6)}$$

3. Implementation of the R_n ratio method as a DigitalMicrograph script program

Within this work the *RAPID-DM* code, initially developed for ImageJ (Weirich, 2024c), was translated into the scripting language of DigitalMicrograph[®], for short DM (GATAN Inc., www.gatan.com). As part of this process, the code was streamlined and optimized, and an improved handling of Kikuchi diffraction patterns was implemented. The disclosed script code allows for any modifications to be made to meet potential adjustments of other users (see (Schaffer, 2016) and (Mitchell) for an introduction to the DM scripting language if needed). The program can be started by loading the script-file directly into the DM platform or for permanent installation and access from the main dropdown menu via the programs 'File / Install Script File' function. Although most of the functionality of *RAPID-DM* has been described in detail elsewhere (see Weirich, 2024c), the following section illustrates the workflow with the here developed script adapted for DM.

3.1 Workflow & User interface

With the aim of user-friendliness, *RAPID-DM* guides the user through all steps from loading a diffraction image to the actual indexing calculation. To illustrate this concept and to visualize the indexing workflow graphically, the input menus are shown in their chronologically order in the flowchart in Figure 1. The program starts with the request to provide the camera constant CC (in $\text{\AA}\cdot\text{pixel}$ units). If CC is set to zero, the program will assume it is 'unknown' and all further calculations and output will be based on lengths in pixel units. If the camera constant CC has been defined, d values will be used in the calculations and listed in the report. The next

menu requires the user to choose between SAED and Kikuchi pattern and opens the file loader to import a user-selected diffraction pattern in DM format for processing. Now the user is required to draw three lines (red, green, and blue) between the pairs of opposite diffraction spots, as described in detail in section 3.2. If the pattern to be analyzed is of the Kikuchi type, the line ROI is automatically replaced by the DM profile marker tool, which allows the orientation and width of the Kikuchi bands to be determined (see Figure 2). To improve the accuracy of the measurement for spot patterns, it is recommended to draw lines between higher order reflections whenever possible. Unlike the ImageJ version of the program, the DM version can handle both even and odd numbers of reflections along each specified line. When using a Kikuchi pattern, the latter dialog will not be shown as only the Kikuchi band width is used for calculation. After defining the pattern geometry, the user is asked to set several parameters that affect the indexing process itself. These are the maximum allowable number for h , k , and l , the allowed deviations (errors) for ratios and angles from the calculated (ideal) values, and the type of Bravais lattice that should be used. Finally, the number of possible solutions can be adjusted by providing a maximum and minimum value for the sum of the hkl indices of the shortest and 2nd shortest lattice vectors (available if the camera constant is undefined), or by specifying a range of allowed lattice parameters (when the camera constant has been provided). However, this lattice parameter is only a rough approximation and not a highly accurate value, as the positions of the spots are determined by mouse clicks on the computer screen. At first sight, this approach may seem too basic, but as will become clear in the later discussion and as will be demonstrated by the examples, this approach is robust, and the involved inaccuracies only increase the allowable errors slightly but have no effect on the reliability of the orientation determination. In addition, this method has the great advantage that it can be easily applied without limitations when the addressed diffraction points exceed the saturation limit or automated methods struggle to detect the center of a diffraction spots. Nevertheless, as the examples in Sections 4.3 and 4.4 show, the lattice parameter provided, even if not very precise, is often very helpful for separating false from true solutions for known structures. Furthermore, this lattice parameter is usually sufficient to perform a database search to identify unknowns if the chemistry of the compound is roughly known. When all required settings for the calculations are complete, the actual indexing process is carried out and the parameters, together with the found solutions are displayed in a results window on the computer monitor. For examples of the results window see the examples in section 4. In parallel with the results window, three files are created and saved in the directory of the processed image:

- An image file containing the original diffraction pattern with the user-defined lines or Kikuchi bands, respectively.
- A file with the complete log containing all information and results from the calculations.
- A comma-separated value (CSV) file containing the key numerical results of the identified solutions, intended for further processing with a spreadsheet program or as input to other programs.

After each run, the user has the option of quitting the program or applying changes to the settings without the need to re-process the diffraction pattern. This allows, for example, to easily test different Bravais lattices with the same parameter setting.

3.2 Guidelines on how to draw the lines for a successful indexing with RAPID-DM

Before proceeding with the examples, some notes are given below on how to correctly assign the reflections for successful indexing. The first step is to identify the three pairs of diffraction spots closest to the center of the SAED pattern. In the example diffraction pattern in Figure 3a, three different sets of reflections are marked by red, green and blue rings. However, there are cases where four reflections have the same distance from the center, so there will only be two rings with distinct reflections. These are, for example, all $\langle 001 \rangle$, all Type II and the $\langle 011 \rangle$ F-lattice zone axis patterns (for the classification of the pattern type the reader is referred to (Weirich, 2024b)). Furthermore, for the very special case of the $\langle 111 \rangle$ zone axis, where all six reflections have the same distance from the pattern center, there will be only one ring with reflections.

In the next step the user is demanded to connect the pairs of symmetry related reflections closest to the center with straight lines (see Figure 3b). This process is repeated three times. The lines connecting the symmetry-related reflections are marked in different colors, red, green and blue, in that order. To increase the accuracy of the determination of the reciprocal vector lengths, the program allows the measurement over several orders of reflexes as mentioned earlier in section 3.1. The corresponding number of reflexes is requested by the program before the actual indexing calculation starts (see program flow-chart in Figure 1). The example in Figure 3b uses just two diffraction spots for each line for clarity of the principle, but we also present other examples here, where higher order reflection pairs have been used (see sections 4.1 and 4.2). The average distances of the diffraction spots from the center r_1 , r_2 and r_3 are then calculated

from the red, green and blue lines by dividing the measured lengths by the number of involved reflections. For drawing the three lines the principal rule is that the pair of reflections that belong to the shortest reciprocal vector (the largest d -value in the data set) must always be drawn first and becomes the red line. Furthermore it is crucial that the next two lines are drawn in the correct orientation to each other so that the hkl indices of the last pair of connected diffraction spots (no. 3 in Figure 3c) is the result from the vector sum of the first two vectors no. 1 (red) and no. 2 (green), as the hkl indices of the blue vector are calculated from eq(4). Hence, in the example in Figure 1b, the green line refers to the 2nd shortest reciprocal space vector and the blue line corresponds to the longest reciprocal space vector among the three reflections. Note that the blue line is drawn to the right of the red line when looking along the red line, and the green line is drawn to the left of the red line to comply with equation (4). To make this principle clearer, the reader is referred to the examples shown in sections 4.1.1 and 4.1.2. For the already mentioned special case of the $\langle 111 \rangle$ zone axis, the order in which the pairs of symmetry related reflections are connected is not relevant.

For Kikuchi pattern analysis, the processing is basically the same as describe above. The only differences are however that the orientation and width of the Kikuchi bands must then be determined using the DM *profile marker* tool (Figure 2) and the option of using higher orders is not available. As before, the user is required to start with the Kikuchi band with the smallest band width, then select the band to the left of the first band with the second smallest band width, and finally the third smallest band width to the right of the first Kikuchi band must be selected (see examples in sections 4.3 and 4.4).

4. Examples

All SAED spot and Kikuchi patterns shown in the following examples were obtained from a FIB cross section sample of silicon investigated in a Jeol JEM-F200 transmission electron microscope (TEM) operated at 200 kV. The patterns were acquired with a GATAN 16-megapixel CMOS OneView® camera and were subsequently inverted and partly contrast enhanced for better visibility of the analyzed Kikuchi lines.

4.1 Spot pattern of silicon $\langle 011 \rangle$

For the SAED pattern shown in Figure 4, the first out of two shortest reciprocal space vectors is defined by the red line connecting the 33-3 and -3-33 reflections. The red line therefore spans over six diffraction points, so that 1/6 of the line length equals the length of the magnified reciprocal vector 11-1 or -1-11 in the pattern. The other reciprocal space vectors -11-1 and 1-11 of the same length as the first, are defined by the green line that connects the diffraction spots -33-3 and 3-33, while the reciprocal space vectors 200 and -200 are defined by the blue line that connects the reflections 400 and -400.

It should be noted that the clearly visible 200 and -200 diffraction spots are forbidden by the symmetry of the $Fd\bar{3}m$ (227) space group of the silicon structure. The presence of these reflections is caused by the quasi-flat Ewald sphere at 200 kV, which allows a near Bragg condition for the forbidden reflection and its higher order reflections, and it is not the result of double diffraction of 11-1 and 1-11 or -11-1 and -1-11 as might be expected at first sight (Zhou & Möllenstedt, 1992). Since the appearance of forbidden reflections is rather the rule than the exception for SAED, the indexing of the diamond lattice of silicon can be usually performed based on the underlying face-centered F-type lattice. Subsequent processing of the data with the RAPID-DM program yielded d -values of 3.126 Å (red), 3.129 Å (green) and 2.731 Å (blue) for the three lines. The therefrom calculated ratios are $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{green}} = 0.999$ and $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{blue}} = 1.145$ and the determined angles between the red and green and red and blue lines are 69.9° and 55.1°. For subsequent indexing, the maximum considered value for h , k and l was set to 2 each, and the allowed ratio and angle errors were 1% and 1° respectively. All three Bravais lattice types (P, I, and F) were tested and the filter for uvw values was set to allow only results where all indices positive. With these settings, the $\langle 011 \rangle$ zone axis for a face-centered cell was directly identified as the only solution. The from the d -values and trial indices calculated averaged lattice parameter is $a = 5.43$ Å. The by RAPID-DM calculated (ideal) ratios for this orientation are $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{green}} = 1.0$ and $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{blue}} = 1.155$. The ideal angles between the reciprocal space vectors for this zone axis are 70.53° and 54.74° (for numerical and graphical verification of the results see (Weirich, 2024a) on page 50).

4.2 Spot pattern of silicon $\langle 112 \rangle$

The principle setup for the SAED pattern shown in Figure 5 and the subsequent processing followed the same path as described in the previous example in Section 4.1. The d -values determined here are 3.114Å, 1.915Å and 1.640Å as calculated from six reflections along the

red line and from four reflections each along the green and blue lines. The corresponding calculated ratios are $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{green}} = 1.626$ and $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{blue}} = 1.898$ and the angles between the red and green lines and the red and blue lines are 89.0° and 59.1° . For this indexing attempt, the maximum allowable values for h , k and l were set to 3 each, while the allowable ratio and angle errors were limited to 1% and 1° respectively. All three Bravais lattice types (P, I and F) were tested and the filter for uvw values was again set to allow only positive values. As for the previous example, the $\langle 112 \rangle$ zone axis for a face-centered cell was readily found as the only solution with a rounded averaged lattice parameter of $a = 5.42 \text{ \AA}$. The ideal ratios for this orientation are $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{green}} = 1.633$ and $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{blue}} = 1.915$ with angles 90° and 58.5° (for numerical and graphical verification of this solution see (Weirich, 2024a) on page 53).

4.3 Kikuchi pattern of silicon $\langle 233 \rangle$ #1729

As described in the guidelines in section 3.2 and shown in Figure 6, the Kikuchi bands were selected by starting with the band of smallest width (red), then moving to the band to the left of the first band with the second smallest band width (green) and finally choosing the band with the third smallest width to the right of the first Kikuchi band (blue). After user confirmation for the correct alignment, each of the Kikuchi bands is identified with a colored line along the center of each band, denoting the orientation of band. The d -values calculated from the widths of the red, green and blue Kikuchi bands are 1.815 \AA , 1.625 \AA and 1.196 \AA in that order. The ratios calculated from these values are $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{green}} = 1.116$ and $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{blue}} = 1.517$ and the corresponding angles between the red and green and the red and the blue bands are determined as 89.9° and 50.1° . For indexing, the maximum allowable values for h , k and l were set to 3 each, while the allowable ratio error had to be increased to 6% to obtain a solution. In contrast to the large ratio error required, the angular deviation could be reduced to 1° to achieve the same result. All three Bravais lattice types (P, I and F) were tested and the filter for uvw indices was again set to allow only positive values. Again, the $\langle 233 \rangle$ zone axis for a face-centered cell was the only solution that matched with the known lattice parameter of silicon. The rounded averaged lattice parameter was $a = 5.25 \text{ \AA}$ in this case. The ideal ratios for the $\langle 233 \rangle$ orientation are $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{green}} = 1.173$ and $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{blue}} = 1.541$ with angles 90° and 49.54° . While the check for the body-centered Bravais lattice gave no results, the test for the primitive lattice yielded with the same settings the orientation $\langle 8\ 9\ 11 \rangle$ with $a = 6.92 \text{ \AA}$. Since the lattice parameter of silicon is known, the latter result for the primitive lattice could be ruled out. To exclude similar results with large deviations to the known lattice parameter RAPID-DM allows

to set upper and lower limits for the lattice parameter as shown in Figure 1 and described in section 3.1. An alternative way to rule out such pseudo-solutions is pattern simulation, *e.g.* with the program JEMS (www.jems-swiss.ch), which usually reveals immediately whether a given solution is a likely one. Another indication that the proposed orientation is doubtful is that the uvw indices for this solution are unusually large. In our experience, trustworthy solutions are usually characterized by the smallest achievable errors and the lowest uvw indices for the orientation. The latter, however, may sometimes override the former, as lattices can be strained, which can significantly increase the necessary error boundaries for a match. As shown by this example, the error for determining the d -value from the manually defined width of the Kikuchi bands is considerably larger than for the spot patterns. Therefore, the calculated averaged lattice parameter of $a = 5.25 \text{ \AA}$ was also assessed to be much too low (ideal value $a = 5.43 \text{ \AA}$, ICDD powder diffraction file #00-027-1402). In contrast, the allowed angular error could be reduced to 1 degree, which indicates that Kikuchi lines are quite reliable for determining the relative angles between the lattice planes, although only very simple tools have been used here for manual measurement.

4.4 Kikuchi pattern of silicon $\langle 125 \rangle$ #1759

The processing of the Kikuchi pattern shown in Figure 7 was carried out in a similar way to that of the pattern in section 4.3. For this pattern, the d -values derived from the widths of the Kikuchi bands were 1.659 \AA , 1.504 \AA and 1.139 \AA , which yielded the calculated ratios $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{green}} = 1.103$ and $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{blue}} = 1.456$ with the angles between the red and green bands and the red and blue bands of 86.2° and 42.8° . The maximum allowable values for h , k and l were set to 3 each for indexing and it was necessary to increase the ratio error to 10% and the misalignment error to 2° to obtain a solution. The check for the F-lattice yielded $\langle 125 \rangle$ for the zone axis with a lattice parameter $a = 5.36 \text{ \AA}$. The ideal ratios for this orientation are $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{green}} = 1.0$ and $d_{\text{red}}/d_{\text{blue}} = 1.499$ with angles 84.78° and 42.39° . The test for the body-centered Bravais lattice with the same setting suggested the orientations $\langle 1\ 5\ 13 \rangle$ and $\langle 5\ 7\ 11 \rangle$, both with $a = 6.03 \text{ \AA}$. In addition to the latter the check for the P-lattice yielded $\langle 6\ 8\ 9 \rangle$ with $a = 5.92 \text{ \AA}$ as a possible solution. The same arguments as in section 4.3. were used to exclude the solutions obtained for the body-centered and primitive lattice, so that only the solution for the F-centered Bravais lattice with orientation along the $\langle 125 \rangle$ was considered as the true solution. A subsequent pattern simulation using JEMS (www.jems-swiss.ch) readily confirmed this result.

5. Discussion and Conclusion

A recently for ImageJ developed program for indexing zone-axis aligned selected area electron diffraction (SAED) spot patterns and TEM Kikuchi patterns (Weirich, 2024c) was translated and adapted to run native on the DigitalMicrograph® platform. This resolves the issue that users with GATAN cameras, who are often not permitted to modify their TEM PC system, are excluded from using the here proposed R_n ratio approach for on-site analysis of diffraction patterns. The translated code has been thoroughly tested for all patterns listed in the Atlas of Zone Axis Spot Patterns for Cubic Lattices (Weirich, 2024a) to ensure that it gives correct results. Nevertheless, an important question for new users of the program may be the accuracy required when manually locating the diffraction spot centers or Kikuchi band widths. To address this issue quantitatively, the spot pattern shown in Figure 4 was analyzed using a dedicated SAED lattice parameter determination program that employs an automated peak location function (Weirich, 2025). The thereby obtained list of 34 d -values from the pattern in Figure 8 was used as input for a LS lattice refinement with the program UnitCell (Holland & Redfern, 1997). The received result of the refined lattice parameter $a = 5.430(7)$ Å is in excellent agreement with the ideal value of $5.43088(4)$ Å (ICDD powder diffraction file #00-027-1402), which was earlier used to calibrate the camera length of the TEM. Comparison of the refined lattice parameter from the automated peak search and that obtained by manually locating only six peak centers (two for each of the three lines) in the spot patterns in Figures 4 and 5 (see also Table 1), shows no significant difference between the two values. Therefore, it is legitimate to argue that the implementation of an automated peak locator function is not needed to determine the lattice parameter with sufficient accuracy. In this context, it should be kept in mind that the main purpose of RAPID-DM is to determine the orientation and not to provide precise lattice parameters, which was beyond the scope of the program development. That the program nevertheless fully meets its objective is shown by comparison of the results in Table 1. Even though the error in the calculation for the Kikuchi pattern had to be increased significantly up to 10% in one case, the correct zone axis orientation was found. This is a clear indication of the robustness of the implemented approach and that the accuracy of the determined lattice parameter, and the underlying distances are less important than it might appear at first sight. However, it must be acknowledged that the accuracy of the manual measurement of the bandwidth of the Kikuchi bands is much more difficult and that there is no averaging with higher order reflexes to improve the accuracy. This is perhaps the most logical explanation for the fact that the ratio errors are significantly higher for Kikuchi diffraction patterns, although the angular errors are still quite small. But there is also another effect associated with Kikuchi diffraction images that should also be considered. Since TEM Kikuchi

diffraction patterns are usually recorded at much shorter camera lengths than SAED spot diffraction patterns, small errors in the measurement will have a much greater effect on the determined values than at longer camera lengths (see eq. 5). This effect leads to further inaccuracies, which require that the error limits for the ratios must be increased. However, our experience with RAPID-DM after indexing several dozen SAED spot patterns, is that the errors are in most cases below 2% for ratios and less than 2° for the angles, unless the pseudo-cubic lattices deviate strongly from the ideal cubic lattices or are severely strained. In this context it should also be mentioned that RAPID-DM provides for each solution a residual calculated from the deviations of the experimental and calculated ratios, and it gives the maximum deviation for the angles (for details on this see (Weirich, 2024c)). Both quality figures are the values in the output window, which are given at the end of each line of a found orientation.

During the analysis of a bunch of Kikuchi diffraction patterns of silicon, we noticed an interesting phenomenon which has the power to prevent the indexing of a pattern, and which might also be of interest for the potential users of RAPID-DM. For the example in 4.1 (Figure 4) it was mentioned that the forbidden 200 reflections appear in the silicon $\langle 011 \rangle$ spot pattern. As we have reported there, the presence of symmetry-forbidden reflexes (in spot pattern) is usually not an issue for the indexing of the diamond type lattice. However, we failed in our attempt to evaluate the Kikuchi diffraction pattern in Figure 9 when using the rules described in the guidelines in Section 3.2, although the spot diffraction pattern in the background could be easily identified as zone axis $\langle 123 \rangle$ with $a = 5.44 \text{ \AA}$ (for verification of the pattern geometry see (Weirich, 2024a) on page 58). A subsequently carried out simulation with the JEMS program (www.jems-swiss.ch) revealed the reason why this Kikuchi diffraction pattern could not be evaluated according to the given rules. As can be seen by comparison of the experimental pattern with the JEMS simulation in Figure 9, the for the indexing required red marked 111 Kikuchi band with the smallest band width is absent in the experimental pattern. Instead, a strong Kikuchi band is seen, which relates to the forbidden 222 reflex (see yellow arrows in the experimental image). Thus, if we strictly apply our rules for the order of the Kikuchi bands, we would erroneously choose the 222 Kikuchi band with twice the band width of the 111 band at first. So even if the next two Kikuchi bands are correctly addressed, the false 222 Kikuchi band will introduce a constant error by factor two into all calculations of the ratios, so the indexing cannot be successful. This example demonstrates that the evaluation of Kikuchi patterns may need to be treated with some caution. Hence, if a Kikuchi pattern cannot be evaluated in a straightforward manner as described, it should be considered that the pattern may have been altered by dynamic or secondary scattering. If, as in this example, there is a spot

diffraction pattern seen in the background of the Kikuchi pattern, indexing can still be carried out to work around such effects.

As demonstrated by several examples for silicon, the RAPID-DM code described in this paper is robust, easy to use, and allows instant verification and testing of the cubic structure of the material and its Bravais lattice type. For calibrated patterns, the cubic lattice parameter is provided for each solution, allowing either phase identification for unknowns by database search (Weirich, 2024c), or for known structures to easily distinguish between true and pseudo solutions. It should be highlighted that although most diffraction patterns recorded in a modern TEM laboratory are calibrated, the R_n ratio method implemented here also has the unique feature of being able to work with uncalibrated diffraction patterns (Weirich, 2024b). With these strengths in mind, it is hoped that the implementation of this approach as a DigitalMicrograph® script will serve as a valuable tool in all TEM laboratories where cubic materials are frequently studied and where GATAN's DigitalMicrograph® is the primary platform for recording and analyzing electron diffraction patterns.

Table 1. Summary of the with RAPID-DM obtained results for silicon.

* The reference value used to calculate the error of the experimental lattice parameter was $a = 5.43088(4) \text{ \AA}$ (ICDD powder diffraction file #00-027-1402).

Example no.	4.1	4.2	4.3	4.4
Figure no.	4	5	6	7
Type of DP	Spot	Spot	Kikuchi	Kikuchi
CC [$\text{\AA} \cdot \text{pixel}$]	1913.6	940.1	529.9	564.0
Bravais lattice	F	F	F	F
RAPID zone axis	$\langle 011 \rangle$	$\langle 112 \rangle$	$\langle 233 \rangle$	$\langle 125 \rangle$
Exp. lattice param. Deviation *	5.43 \AA < 0.1%	5.42 \AA 0.2%	5.25 \AA 3.3%	5.36 \AA 1.3%
$d_{\text{red}} / d_{\text{green}}$ Exp. ratio Ideal ratio Deviation	0.999 1.0 0.1%	1.626 1.633 0.4%	1.116 1.173 4.9%	1.103 1.0 10.3%
$d_{\text{red}} / d_{\text{blue}}$ Exp. value Ideal value Deviation	1.145 1.155 0.9%	1.898 1.915 0.9%	1.517 1.541 1.6%	1.456 1.477 1.4%
red \angle green Exp. angle Ideal angle Deviation	69.9 $^\circ$ 70.53 $^\circ$ 0.6 $^\circ$	89.0 $^\circ$ 90.0 $^\circ$ 1.0 $^\circ$	89.9 $^\circ$ 90.0 $^\circ$ 0.1 $^\circ$	86.2 $^\circ$ 84.78 $^\circ$ 1.4 $^\circ$
red \angle blue Exp. angle Ideal angle Deviation	55.1 $^\circ$ 54.74 $^\circ$ 0.4 $^\circ$	59.1 $^\circ$ 58.52 $^\circ$ 0.6 $^\circ$	50.1 $^\circ$ 49.54 $^\circ$ 0.6 $^\circ$	42.8 $^\circ$ 42.39 $^\circ$ 0.4 $^\circ$

Figure 1. Workflow and user interface of the RAPID version for DigitalMicrograph as described in section 3.1.

Figure 2. For Kikuchi patterns, the standard line ROI for connecting the diffraction spots is replaced by the *profile marker* tool indicated by the dashed rectangle in the image. The width of the profile maker tool, which is used to measure the Kikuchi bandwidth, can be easily adjusted using the controls in the inset. After confirmation of the orientation and band width in the dialogue (not shown), a line (red, green, blue) is drawn in the center of the measured Kikuchi band. The image on the left shows the result after defining the first Kikuchi band in the pattern.

Figure 3. Drawing the lines for correct indexing with RAPID-DM (a) In step one the three sets of diffraction spots closest to the center of the SAED pattern must be identified. The different distances of the diffraction spots from the center are indicated by red, green and blue rings, in that order. (b) In the second step the opposite by 2-fold symmetry related reflections are connected by straight lines. As outlined in the main text, it is crucial for a successful indexing that the correct orientation of the lines is maintained when drawing them. As a rule, the green line is always positioned to the left of the red line, while the blue line is always to its right as illustrated (c) One out of two possible triplets of vectors that can be used for indexing. Note, that the blue vector 3 is the result of the subtraction of vector 1 minus vector 2 according to eq(4).


```

-----
Indexing is done for a cubic F-lattice
WARNING! hkl indices of the two basis vectors are user-restricted to a maximum value of 2 !
WARNING! output is user-restricted to positive [uvw] indices !
WARNING! calculated d-values and lattice parameters are based on the camera constant CC = 1913.6 [Å*Pixel]
WARNING! output contains only unit cells in the range between a(min) = 0 Å and a(max) = 20 Å !
-----

*** INITIAL CALCULATIONS FOR JOB <U:\RAPID_SI DIFFERENT ZA DPS\RAPID_INDEXING_SI (DM-ANALYSIS)\1714_ZA_011\1714.JPG> ***

Type: TEM SAED spot pattern.

d-value of reflection line 1 (red) = 3.126 Å (from 6 reflections)
d-value of reflection line 2 (green) = 3.129 Å (from 6 reflections)
d-value of reflection line 3 (blue) = 2.731 Å (from 4 reflections)

Measured length ratio 2_1 = 0.999, allowed variation: +/- 0.01 (1 %)
Measured angle 2_1 = 69.88°, allowed variation: +/- 1°

Measured length ratio 3_1 = 1.145, allowed variation: +/- 0.011 (1 %)
Measured angle 3_1 = 55.08°, allowed variation: +/- 1°

*** INDEXING ***
a[Å], lattice, [uvw], hkl(1 red), hkl(2 green), hkl(3 blue) ( R-value for ratios [%] ; max. angle deviation [°] )

5.432, F, [0 1 1], -1 -1 1, 1 -1 1, -2 0 0 --- 0.5131 ; 0.65
5.432, F, [1 1 0], -1 1 -1, -1 1 1, 0 0 -2 --- 0.5131 ; 0.65
5.432, F, [1 0 1], -1 1 1, -1 -1 1, 0 2 0 --- 0.5131 ; 0.65
5.432, F, [1 0 1], 1 -1 -1, 1 1 -1, 0 -2 0 --- 0.5131 ; 0.65
5.432, F, [1 1 0], 1 -1 1, 1 -1 -1, 0 0 2 --- 0.5131 ; 0.65
5.432, F, [0 1 1], 1 1 -1, -1 1 -1, 2 0 0 --- 0.5131 ; 0.65
    
```

Figure 4. Steps of processing a $\langle 011 \rangle$ SAED pattern of silicon with RAPID-DM. The top right image shows the diffraction pattern with the user defined lines and subsequently added Laue indices to illustrate the indexing process. Note that the clearly visible 200 and -200 diffraction spots are forbidden by symmetry for the diamond lattice of silicon (see text). The image at the bottom shows the core content of the results window displayed on the computer monitor after the successful run of RAPID-DM for the above pattern.

Figure 5. Steps of processing a $\langle 112 \rangle$ SAED pattern of silicon with RAPID-DM.


```

-----
Indexing is done for a cubic F-lattice
WARNING! hkl indices of the two basis vectors are user-restricted to a maximum value of 3 !
WARNING! output is user-restricted to positive [uvw] indices !
WARNING! calculated d-values and lattice parameters are based on the camera constant CC = 529.9 [Å*Pixel]
WARNING! output contains only unit cells in the range between a(min) = 0 Å and a(max) = 20 Å !
WARNING! Kikuchi patterns may require a significant increase in the range of error for ratios and angles !
-----

*** INITIAL CALCULATIONS FOR JOB <U:\RAPID_SI DIFFERENT ZA DPS\DATA FOR SCIEBO\1729_ZA233_KIKUCHI\1729_ZA233_KIKUCHI.JPG> ***

Type: TEM Kikuchi pattern.

d-value for Kikuchi band 1 (red) = 1.815 Å (from band width)
d-value for Kikuchi band 2 (green) = 1.625 Å (from band width)
d-value for Kikuchi band 3 (blue) = 1.196 Å (from band width)

Measured length ratio 2_1 = 1.116, allowed variation: +/- 0.067 (6 %)
Measured angle 2_1 = 89.88°, allowed variation: +/- 1°

Measured length ratio 3_1 = 1.517, allowed variation: +/- 0.091 (6 %)
Measured angle 3_1 = 50.12°, allowed variation: +/- 1°

*** INDEXING ***
a[Å], lattice, [uvw], hkl(1 red), hkl(2 green), hkl(3 blue) ( R-value for ratios [%] ; max. angle deviation [°] )

5.246, F, [ 3 2 3 ], -2 0 2, 1 -3 1, -3 3 1 --- 3.0763 ; 0.58
5.246, F, [ 3 3 2 ], -2 2 0, -1 -1 3, -1 3 -3 --- 3.0763 ; 0.58
5.246, F, [ 2 3 3 ], 0 -2 2, 3 -1 -1, -3 -1 3 --- 3.0763 ; 0.58
5.246, F, [ 2 3 3 ], 0 2 -2, -3 1 1, 3 1 -3 --- 3.0763 ; 0.58
5.246, F, [ 3 3 2 ], 2 -2 0, 1 1 -3, 1 -3 3 --- 3.0763 ; 0.58
5.246, F, [ 3 2 3 ], 2 0 -2, -1 3 -1, 3 -3 -1 --- 3.0763 ; 0.58
    
```

Figure 6. Steps of processing a $\langle 233 \rangle$ TEM Kikuchi pattern of silicon with RAPID-DM. After indexing the Kikuchi diffraction pattern, the program attempts to locate the expected positions of the spot reflections that belong to each of the Kikuchi bands. The expected positions for a zone axis aligned pattern are marked by circles with the same colors as those used for the corresponding center line of the Kikuchi bands.


```

-----
Indexing is done for a cubic F-lattice
WARNING! hkl indices of the two basis vectors are user-restricted to a maximum value of 3 !
WARNING! output is user-restricted to positive [uvw] indices !
WARNING! calculated d-values and lattice parameters are based on the camera constant CC = 564 [Å*Pixel]
WARNING! output contains only unit cells in the range between a(min) = 0 Å and a(max) = 20 Å !
WARNING! Kikuchi patterns may require a significant increase in the range of error for ratios and angles !
-----

*** INITIAL CALCULATIONS FOR JOB <U:\RAPID_SI DIFFERENT ZA DPS\DATA FOR SCIEBO\1759_ZA125 (KIKUCHI)\1759_ZA125_KIKUCHI.JPG> ***

Type: TEM Kikuchi pattern.

d-value for Kikuchi band 1 (red) = 1.659 Å (from band width)
d-value for Kikuchi band 2 (green) = 1.504 Å (from band width)
d-value for Kikuchi band 3 (blue) = 1.139 Å (from band width)

Measured length ratio 2_1 = 1.103, allowed variation: +/- 0.11 (10 %)
Measured angle 2_1 = 86.15°, allowed variation: +/- 2°

Measured length ratio 3_1 = 1.456, allowed variation: +/- 0.146 (10 %)
Measured angle 3_1 = 42.78°, allowed variation: +/- 2°

*** INDEXING ***
a[Å], lattice, [uvw], hkl(1 red), hkl(2 green), hkl(3 blue) ( R-value for ratios [%] ; max. angle deviation [°] )

5.357, F, [ 1 5 2 ], -3 1 -1, -1 -1 3, -2 2 -4 --- 4.8456 ; 1.37
5.357, F, [ 2 5 1 ], -3 1 1, 1 -1 3, -4 2 -2 --- 4.8456 ; 1.37
5.357, F, [ 2 1 5 ], -1 -3 1, 3 -1 -1, -4 -2 2 --- 4.8456 ; 1.37
5.357, F, [ 5 1 2 ], -1 -1 3, 1 -3 -1, -2 2 4 --- 4.8456 ; 1.37
5.357, F, [ 5 2 1 ], -1 1 3, 1 -3 1, -2 4 2 --- 4.8456 ; 1.37
5.357, F, [ 1 2 5 ], -1 3 -1, -3 -1 1, 2 4 -2 --- 4.8456 ; 1.37
5.357, F, [ 1 2 5 ], 1 -3 1, 3 1 -1, -2 -4 2 --- 4.8456 ; 1.37
5.357, F, [ 5 2 1 ], 1 -1 -3, -1 3 -1, 2 -4 -2 --- 4.8456 ; 1.37
5.357, F, [ 5 1 2 ], 1 1 -3, -1 3 1, 2 -2 -4 --- 4.8456 ; 1.37
5.357, F, [ 2 1 5 ], 1 3 -1, -3 1 1, 4 2 -2 --- 4.8456 ; 1.37
5.357, F, [ 2 5 1 ], 3 -1 -1, -1 1 -3, 4 -2 2 --- 4.8456 ; 1.37
5.357, F, [ 1 5 2 ], 3 -1 1, 1 1 -3, 2 -2 4 --- 4.8456 ; 1.37
    
```

Figure 7. Steps of processing a $\langle 125 \rangle$ TEM Kikuchi pattern of silicon with RAPID-DM.

Figure 8. Analysis of the original $\langle 011 \rangle$ SAED pattern in Figure 4 with the program UnitCellSAED (Weirich, 2025) to determine the most accurate lattice parameters via automated peak location. The derived interplanar d -values were used for LS lattice refinement with the program UnitCell (Holland & Redfern, 1997) (see text for more details).

Figure 9. A (123) TEM Kikuchi pattern of silicon (top) and its corresponding kinematic simulated pattern obtained with the JEMS program (www.jems-swiss.ch) at the bottom. The yellow spots in the underlying spot pattern refer to forbidden reflection in the diamond type structure of silicon. Comparison of the experimental pattern with the simulation shows that the in red marked 111 Kikuchi band is missing in the experimental image, which is the reason for the failure of the indexing attempt with the Kikuchi bands. Instead, a strong Kikuchi band, that is related to the forbidden 222 reflex, is seen (see yellow arrows in the experimental DP). The higher order 333 Kikuchi band shown in green in the simulation appears in both, the experimental and simulated pattern. In contrast to the Kikuchi part of the pattern, the spot diffraction pattern in the background could be easily indexed by RAPID-DM (see section 5. for details).

Availability of the script code

The script code will be released at <https://zenodo.org> under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International Licence upon acceptance of the manuscript for publication.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Vasilis A. Maroufidis: Data measurement, Data Curation, Software, Validation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Thomas E. Weirich:** Conceptualization, Software, Funding acquisition, Methodology, Resources, Validation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this contribution.

Acknowledgements

This development of the script code has been carried out within Collaborative Research Centre Transregio 188: Damage Controlled Forming Processes (DFG - German Research Foundation, Project-ID 278868966).

References

- Andrews, K. W., Dyson, D. J. & Keown, S. R. (1968). Interpretation of electron diffraction patterns, 2nd ed. London: Adam Hilger.
- Bragg, W. L. (1913). Proc. R. Soc. A, 89, 248-276.
- Champness, P. E. (2001). Electron diffraction in the transmission electron microscope. London: Taylor & Francis.
- Edington, J. W. (1975). Electron diffraction in the electron microscope, Philips Technical Library, Monographs in Practical Electron Microscopy in Materials Science, Vol. 2. Eindhoven: N. V. Philips' Gloeilampenfabrieken
- Eichen, E., Laird, C. and Bitler, W.R. Reciprocal Lattice Diffraction Patterns for F.C.C., B.C.C., and H.C.P., and Diamond Cubic Crystal Systems), Ford Scientific Laboratory, Detroit, Michigan, USA. (unknown date of publication)

Fultz, B. & Howe, J. M. (2002). *Transmission Electron Microscopy and Diffractometry of Materials*, 2nd ed. Berlin: Springer-Verlag.

Heimendahl, M. (1980). *Electron microscopy of Materials: An Introduction*. New York: Academic Press.

Holland, T. J. B., Redfern, S. A. T. (1997). Unit cell refinement from powder diffraction data: the use of regression diagnostics. *Mineralogical Magazine*, 61(404), 65-77.
DOI: [10.1180/minmag.1997.061.404.07](https://doi.org/10.1180/minmag.1997.061.404.07)

Mitchell, D., <http://www.dmscripting.com/>

Schaffer, B. (2016). Digital Micrograph. In: Carter, C., Williams, D. (eds) *Transmission Electron Microscopy*. Springer, Springer International Publishing Switzerland.
DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-26651-0_6](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-26651-0_6)

Spence, J. C. H. & Zuo, J. M. (1992). *Electron Microdiffraction*. New York: Plenum Press.

Weirich, T. E. (2024a). *Atlas of Zone Axis Spot Patterns for Cubic Lattices*, RWTH Publications, RWTH Aachen University, Aachen, Germany.
DOI: [10.18154/RWTH-2024-02030](https://doi.org/10.18154/RWTH-2024-02030)

Weirich, T. E. (2024b). A simple protocol for determining the zone axis direction from selected-area electron diffraction spot patterns of cubic materials, *J. Appl. Cryst.* (2024). 57, 1263–1269. DOI: [10.1107/S1600576724004333](https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600576724004333)

Weirich, T. E. (2024c). RAPID, an ImageJ macro for indexing electron diffraction zone axis spot patterns of cubic materials, *J. Appl. Cryst.* (2024). 57, 2017–2029.
DOI: [10.1107/S1600576724010215](https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600576724010215)

Weirich, T.E. (2025). *UnitCellSAED – An ImageJ-Based Tool for Determining Unit Cell Parameters from Selected Area Electron Diffraction Patterns*. Technical Report No. 1-2025, Central Facility for Electron Microscopy, RWTH Aachen University.
DOI: [10.18154/RWTH-2025-04291](https://doi.org/10.18154/RWTH-2025-04291)

Williams, D. B. & Carter, C. B. (2009). *Transmission Electron Microscopy: A Textbook for Materials Science*. New York: Springer

West, A. R. (2014). *Solid state chemistry and its applications*. 2nd ed. Chichester: Wiley.

Zhao, Y, Al-Fahdi, M., Hu, M., Siriwardane, E.M.D., Song, Y., Nasiri, A., Hu, J. (2021). High-Throughput Discovery of Novel Cubic Crystal Materials Using Deep Generative Neural Networks. *Adv. Sci.*, 8, 2100566. DOI: [10.1002/advs.202100566](https://doi.org/10.1002/advs.202100566)

F. Zhou, F., Möllenstedt, G. (1992). *Ultramicroscopy*, 41(4), 359-366.